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3 **An Extreme Wave Event in eastern Yucatán, Mexico: evidence of a paleotsunami event**
4 **during the Mayan times**
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7 Javier Lario¹, Chris Spencer², Teresa Bardají³, Ángel Marchante⁴, Victor H. Garduño-Monroy⁵,
8 Jorge Macias⁶, Sergio Ortega⁷.
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12 1. Facultad de Ciencias, UNED, Spain. e-mail: javier.lario@ccia.uned.es

13
14 2. Geography and Environmental Management, UWE, Bristol, UK

15
16 3. Departamento de Geología, Geografía y Medio Ambiente, Universidad de Alcalá, Spain.

17
18 3. Grupo de Investigación TARHA, Universidad de las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain.

19
20 5. Departamento de Geología y Mineralogía, Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de
21 Hidalgo, México.

22
23 6. Depto. de A.M., E. e I.O. y Matemática Aplicada, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de
24 Málaga, Spain.

25
26 7. Laboratorio de Métodos Numéricos, SCAI, Universidad de Málaga, Spain.
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28 **ABSTRACT**
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30 The Yucatán Peninsula, Mexico, has typically been considered a tectonically stable region
31 without significant seismic activity, in contrast, the region is one that is regularly affected by
32 hurricanes. A detailed survey of ca. 100 km of the eastern Yucatan and Cozumel coast
33 identified the presence of ridges containing individual boulders measuring >1 m, with up to
34 three ridges at some locations. The ridges reach five metres in height and their origin is
35 associated with Extreme Wave Event (EWE) activity. Previously modelled tsunami waves from
36 known seismically active zones in the region (Muertos Thrust Belt and South Caribbean
37 Deformed Belt) are not of sufficient scale in the area of the Yucatan peninsula to have
38 produced the boulder ridges recorded in this study. The occurrence of hurricanes in this region
39 is more common, but two of the most destructive (Hurricane Gilbert 1988 and Hurricane
40 Wilma 2005) produced coastal waves too small to have created the ridges recorded here. In
41 this paper, a new tsunami model has been generated that indicates a tsunami event may have
42 caused the EWE that resulted in the deposition of the boulder ridges.
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47 Key words: Extreme Wave Event, tsunami, boulders, paleoseismology.
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50 **INTRODUCTION**
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52 The Yucatan Peninsula of Mexico is a carbonate platform comprised of Eocene-age limestone
53 in the interior, with off-lapping sequences to a Quaternary coastline (Weidie, 1985). The
54 present-day coastline is incised into the Pleistocene shelf margin, reef, and back-reef
55 limestones, which were deposited during the last interglacial sea level highstand (marine
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3 isotope stage -MIS 5). The Pleistocene deposits extend inland for some 10 km and form the
4 most recent of a sequence of accreted carbonate units reaching at least 12 m thick (Ward,
5 1985).

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7 The Peninsula is considered to have been tectonically stable since the late Pleistocene (Szabo
8 et al., 1978), this belief is also supported by the lack of recorded historical seismicity (Marquez-
9 Azua et al., 2004).

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11 A detailed survey of ca. 100 km of the eastern Yucatan coast (Quintana Roo and Cozumel
12 Island) identified the presence of beach ridges comprised of individual boulders measuring >1
13 m (Figure 1). The ridges reach five metres in height and their origin is inferred to be associated
14 to Extreme Wave Event (EWE) activity, either tsunamis (not recorded as having occurred in the
15 area) or hurricanes (frequently recorded in the area). These boulder ridges were recently
16 partially described by Shaw and Benson (2015) and associated to a tsunami event, but no
17 evidence of the tsunami source was provided.
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19 20 21 **BOULDER RIDGES**

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23 There are two main areas where boulder ridges were studied in detail: the coast in Quintana
24 Roo between Playa del Carmen and Caleta Tankah and the eastern coast of Cozumel Island
25 (Figure 1).
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27 The ridges are composed of accumulations of coral reef boulders, most of them imbricated.
28 Individual boulders are more than 1 m length and the ridges reach heights of 5 m.
29 Accumulations of boulders are more extensive along more rocky sections of the coastline,
30 rocky platforms and capes, whilst in caletas (karstic bays) the boulder ridges are absent instead
31 a ridge of sand, reef pebbles and cobbles is present. Typically, the boulders originate from joint
32 bounded blocks (JBB) originally forming part of the late Pleistocene platforms near msl. At
33 some of the sites a second smaller ridge exists overlapping the main one, the smaller ridges
34 are typically composed of pebbles and cobbles.
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37 More than 100 boulders have been measured (a, b and c dimensions, height, distance to the
38 sea and main lithology) and photographed for photogrammetry using Agisoft Photoscan
39 software (Agisoft, 2017). As a result of the photogrammetry a 3D reconstruction of the
40 boulders was created and all of the dimension can be calculated from them. Thus, the volume
41 of these boulders can be measured accurately (Figure 2). The blocks and boulders represent
42 heterogeneous reef-rock and consist of varying percentages of several different lithofacies.
43 The bulk density of similar deposits has been determined to be between 2.07-2.40 g/cm³ by
44 Engel and May (2012).
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48 **MODELLING BOULDER TRANSPORT**

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50 Several studies have tried to infer the height of wave required to transport boulders at the
51 coast. Nott (1997 2003), assert that the pre-transport situation of a coastal boulder, relative to
52 mean water level, along with its shape, size and density determines the height of wave
53 required for it to be transported. Therefore, the Nott (2003) studies presented formulas to
54 calculate the height of wave required to move boulders by both tsunami and storm waves in
55 three different pre-transport situations: submerged boulders, sub-aerial boulder and joint
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3 bounded blocks. Noormets et al. (2004) noted that tsunami waves have a considerably longer
4 wave period than storm waves, and thus, may have greater transporting capacities because
5 each wave has the potential to transport blocks for a longer time than a storm wave. Indeed,
6 storm waves can break and emplace megaclasts but they tend to attenuate faster than
7 tsunami waves. Pignatielli et al. (2009) introduced some modifications to Nott's (2003)
8 formulas to incorporate the fact that the boulder has one side facing the wave and one top
9 surface and is limited by four sides. Later Barbano et al. (2010) also modified this proposal
10 after testing the wave transport equations on the coast of Sicily. Nandasena et al. (2011)
11 improved Nott's equations further and found that the minimum flow velocity required to
12 initiate the transport of submerged boulders from the revised equation was less than that
13 from Nott's equations (e.g. reduced wave height required by up to 56% for submerged
14 boulders and 65% for joint bounded blocks). Also, they developed a "boulder transport
15 histogram" to represent the range of flow velocity that satisfies the requirements for initial
16 transport of a boulder via different modes of transport: sliding, rolling, and saltation. This
17 boulder transport histogram can be used to predict the possible initial transport modes of a
18 boulder from the flow velocity. Engel and May (2012) reviewed and applied the Nandasena et
19 al. (2011) in Bonaire (Caribe) and the results indicated that boulder weight and dimension, and
20 thus calculated wave energy and wave heights were overestimated in most of the previous
21 studies. Also, as Spiske et al. (2008), they concluded that realistic bulk densities are critical for
22 inferring minimum storm and tsunami wave heights from the boulder record.
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28 ***Height of the extreme wave***

29 Taking into account all of these formulas, and because most of the boulders examined in this
30 study correspond to a JBB scenario, the equations below have been utilised:
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32 Nott (2003) proposal for JBB scenario, where:

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$$34 \quad H_t \geq \frac{0.25 \left(\frac{\rho_b - \rho_w}{\rho_w} \right) a}{C_L}$$

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$$38 \quad H_s \geq \frac{\left(\frac{\rho_b - \rho_w}{\rho_w} \right) a}{C_L}$$

$$39$$

$$40$$

41 where H_t = height of tsunami wave; H_s = height of storm wave; C_L =coefficient of lift=0.178; a = A
42 axis of boulder; ρ_b = density of boulder; ρ_w = density of sea water= 1.02 g/ml.
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44 The proposal of Engel and May (2012) based on the modifications to Nott by Nandasena et al.
45 (2011) for JBB scenario, where:
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$$47 \quad H_t = \frac{(\rho_b - \rho_w) \cdot V \cdot (\cos \theta + \mu \cdot \sin \theta)}{2 \cdot \rho_w \cdot C_L \cdot a \cdot b \cdot q}$$

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$$50 \quad H_s = \frac{(\rho_b - \rho_w) \cdot V \cdot (\cos \theta + \mu \cdot \sin \theta)}{0.5 \cdot \rho_w \cdot C_L \cdot a \cdot b \cdot q}$$

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$$52$$

53 where V =corrected boulder volume; q =boulder area coefficient 0.73; b =B axis of boulder;
54 μ =coefficient of static friction 0.65; θ =angle of the bed slope of the pre-transport setting.
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Table 1 presents the results from the main characteristic boulders (by weight, distance to the sea or altitude). The results using the Engel and May (2012) proposal for JBB scenarios demonstrated that to move the heaviest and largest boulders the height of a tsunami wave would need to be between 2.0 and 2.9 m. In addition, the height of storm wave must be between 8.0 and 11.5 m. Using the Nott (2003) formulas for the same scenario the results in general show an underestimation of the wave height in both cases.

Flow velocity and flow depth required to move the boulders

For the “boulder transport histogram” introduced by Nandasena et al. (2011) in the case of a submerged or subaerial boulder, transport begins with sliding and

$$u^2 \geq \frac{2(\rho b/\rho w - 1)gc(\mu_s \cos \theta + \sin \theta)}{C_d(c/b) + \mu_s C_L}$$

when transport begins with rolling (overturning),

$$u^2 \geq \frac{2(\rho b/\rho w - 1)gc(\cos \theta + (c/b) \sin \theta)}{C_d(c^2/b^2) + C_L}$$

when transport begins with saltation,

$$u^2 \geq \frac{2(\rho b/\rho w - 1)gc \cos \theta}{C_L}$$

in the case of a joint-bounded block, transport begins with lifting,

$$u^2 \geq \frac{2(\rho b/\rho w - 1)gc(\cos \theta + \mu_s \sin \theta)}{C_L}$$

where u is the flow velocity, g is the gravitational acceleration (9.81 m/s^2), μ_s is the coefficient of static friction between the boulder and the bed (0.7), C_d is the coefficient of drag (1.95) (Nandasena et al., 2011; 2014).

To estimate the flow depth from the minimum flow velocity required to move the boulder Nandasena et al. (2014) proposed a relationship between flow depth and flow velocity described by the Froude number as $Fr = u/\sqrt{gh}$, where h is the flow depth. The Froude number for past tsunamis has been determined as between 0.7 and 2.0, in this study the values 1.0 and 1.5 were used as proposed by Nandasena et al., (2012, 2014).

Table 2 presents the results applying these formulas to the main characteristics of boulders examined in this study (weight, distance to the sea or altitude) and Figure 3 presents the “boulder transport histogram” for these same boulders.

Table 2 and figure 3 display the minimum flow velocity and range of flow velocities to initiate boulder transport at each site. The average results display not less than 3.0 m/s at the pre-transport location of the boulders prior to the EWE. If the average flow velocity was higher than 3.0 m/s, the boulders would have been transported by sliding. If the average flow velocity was higher than 4.3 m/s, the boulders would have been transported by rolling, higher than 9.1 m/s by saltation and, in the situation of JBB, as is the case, higher than 9.3 m/s by lifting.

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3 Table 2 also indicates the flow depth necessary to initiate boulder transport using the models
4 applied here. Nandasena et al. (2014) indicate the difficulty in establishing the Froude number
5 at each site. With the proposed $F_r=1.0$ the minimum flow depth to initiate the transport by
6 sliding ranges from 0.4-2.1 m (average 1.0 m), by rolling 0.6-5.3 m (average 2.1 m), by saltation
7 2.6-16.5 m (average 8.8) and by lifting, as is the case for JBB, the flow depth must be between
8 2.7 and 17.1 m (average 9.1 m). With $F_r=1.5$ the minimum flow depth to initiate the transport
9 by sliding ranges between 0.2-0.9 m (average 0.4 m), by rolling 0.2-2.3 m (average 0.9 m), by
10 saltation 1.2-7.3 m (average 3.9 m). By lifting the minimum flow depth ranges between 1.2 and
11 7.6 m (average 4.0 m), a value more applicable to the boulder ridges recorded in this study.
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14 **TSUNAMI VS. HURRICANE ORIGIN**

15 ***Seismicity and hurricanes in Yucatan***

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18 The Yucatan Peninsula is considered a tectonically stable area at least since the late
19 Pleistocene (Szabo et al., 1978). The Mexican Seismic Service (SSS, 2018) has only registered
20 four earthquakes in the Yucatan Peninsula since 1990, and all with M_w lower than 4.6.
21 Tsunami catalogues in the Caribbean area show no recorded events for the Quintana Roo
22 coast (compiled in Engel et al., 2016). The tsunamigenic earthquakes in the Caribbean Plate are
23 mostly concentrated along the western (Lesser Antilles), north-western (Muertos Thrust Belt)
24 and south-western (South Caribbean Deformed Belt) plate boundaries (NOAA, 2018).
25 However, models of tsunami propagation (Engel et al., 2016) show that a tsunami generated
26 by a M_w 7.9 earthquake from the Muertos Thrust Belt (MTB) cannot reach the Yucatan coast.
27 Moreover, a tsunami triggered by a M_w 8.8 earthquake from the South Caribbean Deformed
28 Belt (SCBD) would reach the north-eastern Yucatan coast with a wave height <1.0 m, thus not
29 high enough to produce the boulder ridges investigated in this study.
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33 A different source of seismic activity is required, therefore, generate a tsunami wave able to
34 reach the eastern coast of Yucatan and thus, to confirm the tsunami origin for these boulder
35 ridges. Two recent events off coast of Honduras (M_w 7.3, 2009 and M_w 7.6, 2018; USGS, 2018)
36 and a third one in Guatemala (M_w 7.5, 1976; USGS, 2018) are associated to the Motagua/Swan
37 Island Fault System (MSFS), identifying this as a possible source for a tsunamigenic earthquake.
38 Likewise, two late Holocene $M>7$ earthquakes, have been also reported by Cox et al., (2008)
39 before the occurrence of the 2009 and 2018 events, leading these authors to propose a 1000
40 yr recurrence interval for large earthquakes ($M_w>7$) associated with the MSFS.
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43 The MSFS is a left-lateral strike-slip fault, segment of the boundary between North America
44 and Caribbean plates, which accommodates about 20mm/yr slip (USGS, 2018). However, the
45 instrumental and paleoseismic earthquake records presented above indicate that despite the
46 relatively low slip rate of the MSFS, the resulting seismic and tsunami potential can be
47 significant.
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49 The occurrence of hurricanes in this region is more common, and Yucatan Peninsula is exposed
50 to an average of 20 tropical cyclones each 150 year (Rosengaus Moshinsky et al., 2014). In
51 order to characterize the extreme wave climate and storm surge in the Mexican Pacific Ocean
52 and Gulf of Mexico/Caribbean Sea, Meza-Padilla et al. (2015) modelled a total of 3100
53 synthetic events achieving landfall in Mexico (divided between both basins) and found that the
54 highest waves are expected in the Mexican Caribbean and the northern coast of the Gulf of
55 Mexico whilst the highest storm surge is in the northern part of the Yucatan Peninsula. Two of
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3 the most destructive hurricanes to have made landfall in the Eastern Yucatan produced 4-8 m
4 high waves at the coast and inundation up to 5 km inland (Hurricane Gilbert, 1988, Rosengaus
5 Moshinsky and Sánchez Sesma, 1990) and 8-10 m high waves at the coast (Hurricane Wilma,
6 2005, Alva González, 2015), however coastal waves of this scale are still too small to have
7 produced the ridges recorded in this study.
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9 ***Modelling a tsunami in eastern Yucatan Peninsula***

10 A model of a tsunami generated by a seismic event from the Motagua fault has been
11 generated simulating an earthquake Mw 7.6, 19 km depth with a 110 km length and 26 km
12 width rupture area. The numerical code used is Tsunami-HySEA, this is a GPU-based shallow
13 water code, developed by the EDANYA Group (University of Málaga) and extensively
14 benchmarked for tsunami simulations (Macías et al., 2017). For the numerical simulation, a
15 two-way nested mesh technique (as in Macías et al., 2016) is used. The global mesh that
16 covers the computational domain has a resolution of 15 arc sec (~450m). Then six nested
17 meshes, with an enhanced resolution of 0.9375 arc sec (~28 m) are used in the coastal strip to
18 better assess tsunami wave height in this region.
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21 Results at x32 resolution show that a wave height ca. 2.0 m would be generated in the studied
22 area (Figure 4). Therefore, it is reasonable to assign the main boulder ridge to a tsunami
23 generated by an earthquake Mw > 7.6 offshore in the eastern Caribbean sector of the
24 Motagua fault. The smaller ridge overlapping the main boulder ridge was generated by the
25 Hurricane Wilma in 2005 (witness's communication), demonstrating that destructive
26 Hurricanes do not have sufficient energy in this area to generate the large boulder ridges
27 recorded.
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30 Applying the proposed intensity scale of Tsunami Environmental Effects (TEE-16 Scale, Lario et
31 al., 2016), the tsunami intensity observed in the study area would be VI-VII (slightly damaging-
32 damaging), but this is not the maximum intensity because the area is some considerable
33 distance from the source.
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35 ***Tsunami age and paleoseismic implications***

36 Dating of wave-emplaced blocks and boulders is still a challenge (Terry et al., 2013; Engel et al.,
37 2016; Rixhon et al., in press). Also, the coral ridges and single boulders recorded in this study
38 may have a complex, long-term history of transport, accumulation, and modification during
39 several strong storms and tsunamis (Morton et al., 2008; Scheffers et al., 2014; Rixhon et al., in
40 press). Therefore, it is a challenge to provide a definitive date for the boulder emplacement in
41 the ridges without finding shells, such as *lithophaga*, attached to the boulders prior to their
42 transportation. Shaw and Benson (2015) recorded and dated peat deposits beneath the
43 boulder ridge in the Akumal area and so pre-dating the main boulder ridge near Akumal. ¹⁴C
44 dating provides 2σ calibrated ages for two samples (1390–1567 and 1348–1613 cal YBP)
45 suggesting that the tsunami event took place between ca.500-800 AD, during the late Classic
46 period. In some locations within the region, it is possible observe Mayan buildings constructed
47 over and therefore post-dating, the boulder ridges, for example in the Xcaret complex or Punta
48 Chile (SW XpuHa, Figure 5). Despite the different phases of construction, these remains are
49 Costa oriental in style (Eastern coast), meaning post classic Maya period, between 900-1521
50 AD (Andrews and Andrews, 1975: Covarrubias and Rojas, pers.comm,). This reinforces the date
51 of the event as being between 500-900 AD. It is remarkable that there is no evidence of
52 settlements prior to the post-classic period in this coastal area, and it may be that any small
53 settlements that did exist were affected and covered by the tsunami deposits. This is also
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3 supported by Cox et al., (2008) who found evidence of a large earthquake $M_w > 7.0$ triggered in
4 the MSFS in 900 AD in uplifted coral reef platforms, the event affected at least the north coast
5 of Honduras.

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7 The confirmation of a likely tsunami event caused by a $M_w > 7.6$ earthquake on the Motagua
8 fault implies that even if a long recurrence interval exists, destructive tsunami episodes can
9 reach the eastern Yucatan coast. Despite the belief that the area has been tectonically stable
10 since the late Pleistocene this study found more evidence of seismic activity during Mayan
11 times, such as archeoseismological features located in Mayan sites (tilted walls, “antiseismic”
12 fabric...), evidence of seismic events in submerged caves systems (tilted speleothems, collapses
13 and orientated speleothems...) as well as faults affecting the late Pleistocene and Holocene
14 reef deposits (eastern Cozumel), that are still being investigated (Lario et al., 2017).
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18 CONCLUSIONS

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20 A semi-continuous boulder ridge up to 5 m a.s.l, has been recorded on the eastern coast of the
21 Yucatan Peninsula and Cozumel Island, generated by an Extreme Wave Event. The application
22 of different approaches demonstrates that waves of between 2.0-2.9 m (in the case of a
23 tsunami origin) and between 8.0-11.5 m (in the case of storm/hurricane origin) would need to
24 be generated to result in the accumulation of these boulder ridges. Most of the possible
25 tsunami source areas located in East Caribbean are not capable of generating a tsunami that
26 would reach the Yucatan coast. However, as demonstrated through model simulation in this
27 study, the Motagua Fault section located in the SW Caribbean basin can generate a tsunami
28 with waves of between 2.0-3.0 m height at the eastern Yucatan coast, resulting from an
29 earthquake of $>M_w 7.6$.
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32 This and other evidence, demonstrates the occurrence of seismic activity during late
33 Pleistocene and Holocene in the Eastern Yucatan Peninsula and surrounding areas illustrating
34 the necessity to review all mitigation protocols in this area related to seismic and tsunami
35 hazards.
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6 Figure 1; a) Location map of the boulder ridges; b) Boulder ridge at Punta Venado (PV). c)
7 Boulders at eastern Cozumel. Sites: XT: Xcaret, PV: Punta Venado, PA: Paamul, XH: XpuHa, KA:
8 Kantenah, PL: Palladium Resort, XC: Xcaceel, CT: Caleta Tankah.
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10 Figure 2. Agisoft photogrammetry of some boulders in the Akumal Sector. All of the
11 measurements used in this study can be obtained from the 3D reconstructions.
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19 Figure 5. Post classic Maya remains SW XpuHa upper the boulder ridge.
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Tables

Table 1. Height of the extreme wave (tsunami and storm) necessary to move the boulders listed.

Table 2. Minimum flow velocity and flow depth to initiate boulder transport in different transport modes and using different Froude numbers ($F_r=1$; $F_r=1.5$).

Sector	Boulder	a	b	c	Corrected vol.	Weight kg	Nott - JBB		Engel and May – JBB	
							Ht	Hs	Ht	Hs
Paamul	BPM1	1.89	1.39	0.51	0.66	1490	1.0	4.0	1.2	4.9
	BPM2	1.19	0.46	0.46	0.12	280	0.1	0.6	1.1	4.4
	BPM3	1.37	0.81	0.45	0.24	555	0.4	1.7	1.1	4.3
	BPM5	0.84	0.80	0.70	0.23	523	0.3	1.0	1.7	6.7
	BPM6	1.48	1.14	0.74	0.61	1389	0.5	2.0	1.8	7.1
	BPM7	1.72	0.82	0.49	0.34	769	0.4	1.6	1.2	4.7
	BPM8	1.57	0.98	0.55	0.41	941	0.5	2.0	1.3	5.2
	BPM9	2.70	2.60	1.07	3.68	8355	1.6	6.5	2.6	10.2
	BPM10	3.70	1.72	0.80	2.49	5663	1.1	4.3	1.9	7.6
	B2-3	1.52	1.09	0.64	0.52	1179	0.5	2.1	1.5	6.1
	B2-4	0.85	0.77	0.53	0.17	386	0.3	1.3	1.3	5.1
	B2-5	1.26	0.90	0.58	0.32	732	0.4	1.6	1.4	5.5
	BPM11	2.00	0.74	0.57	0.41	938	0.3	1.2	1.4	5.4
Xcachel	BXC4	1.24	0.60	0.56	0.20	463	0.2	0.8	1.3	5.3
	B2	1.20	0.65	0.61	0.23	529	0.2	0.8	1.5	5.8
	B6	1.80	0.93	0.77	0.63	1434	0.3	1.3	1.8	7.3
	BA12	1.82	1.00	0.84	0.75	1700	0.4	1.4	2.0	8.0
	BN1	1.90	1.00	0.75	0.70	1585	0.4	1.6	1.8	7.2
	BN3	0.90	0.58	0.40	0.10	232	0.2	1.0	1.0	3.8
	BN5	1.40	1.17	0.76	0.61	1385	0.5	2.0	1.8	7.3
	BN6	2.02	1.20	0.42	0.50	1132	0.9	3.7	1.0	4.0
Cozumel	BCZ5	1.50	0.97	0.51	0.36	825	0.5	2.1	1.2	4.9
	BCZ6	3.70	2.38	0.82	3.54	8032	1.9	7.4	2.0	7.8
	BCZ7	1.90	1.60	1.20	1.79	4058	0.6	2.4	2.9	11.5
	BCZ8	2.00	1.90	0.30	0.56	1268	2.4	9.8	0.7	2.9
	BCZ9	2.49	2.00	0.70	1.71	3877	1.5	5.9	1.7	6.7
Palladium	BPA1	1.96	0.91	0.87	0.76	1726	0.3	1.1	2.1	8.3
	BPA2	1.60	1.30	0.95	0.97	2198	0.5	2.0	2.3	9.1
	BPA3	1.84	0.93	0.77	0.65	1466	0.3	1.3	1.8	7.3
	BPA4	1.50	0.95	0.57	0.40	903	0.5	1.8	1.4	5.4
	BPA5	1.86	0.92	0.89	0.75	1694	0.3	1.1	2.1	8.5
	BPA7	1.10	0.55	0.50	0.15	336	0.2	0.7	1.2	4.8
	BPA8	3.90	1.45	0.57	1.58	3585	1.1	4.3	1.4	5.4
	BPA9	2.10	1.00	1.00	1.03	2336	0.3	1.2	2.4	9.5
	BPA10	2.60	1.65	1.08	2.27	5154	0.7	2.9	2.6	10.3
	BPA11	2.30	1.30	0.71	1.04	2361	0.7	2.7	1.7	6.8
Akumal	BAK2	2.32	1.32	0.49	0.74	1669	1.0	3.9	1.2	4.7
	BAK3	2.02	1.00	0.84	0.83	1887	0.4	1.4	2.0	8.0
	BAK4	1.47	1.00	0.87	0.63	1423	0.3	1.3	2.1	8.3
	BAK5	1.30	1.24	0.38	0.30	681	1.0	4.0	0.9	3.6
	BAK6	1.38	1.02	0.86	0.59	1346	0.4	1.4	2.1	8.2

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Kantenah	BKAN1	2.10	0.86	0.76	0.67	1527	0.3	1.2	1.8	7.3
	BKAN2	1.24	0.90	0.47	0.26	583	0.5	1.9	1.1	4.5
	BKAN4	3.10	2.01	0.70	2.14	4852	1.6	6.2	1.7	6.7
	BKAN5	2.12	1.30	0.52	0.70	1594	0.9	3.6	1.2	5.0
	BKAN8	1.21	0.78	0.41	0.19	430	0.4	1.7	1.0	3.9
	BKAN9	2.30	2.10	0.51	1.21	2740	2.0	8.1	1.2	4.9
	BKAN10	2.70	1.56	1.00	2.06	4685	0.7	2.8	2.4	9.5

Boulder ID	Minimum Flow velocity to initiate boulder transport (m/s)				Minimum flow depth to initiate boulder transport (m)							
					$F_T=1.0$				$F_T=1.5$			
	sliding	rolling	saltation	lifting	slid.	roll.	saltat.	lift.	slid.	roll.	saltat.	lift.
BPM1	3.3	5.3	8.3	8.4	1.1	2.9	7.0	7.3	0.5	1.3	3.1	3.2
BPM2	2.0	2.3	7.9	8.0	0.4	0.6	6.3	6.6	0.2	0.2	2.8	2.9
BPM3	2.6	3.8	7.8	7.9	0.7	1.5	6.2	6.4	0.3	0.6	2.8	2.9
BPM5	2.6	3.2	9.7	9.9	0.7	1.1	9.6	10.0	0.3	0.5	4.3	4.4
BPM6	3.1	4.3	10.0	10.2	1.0	1.9	10.2	10.5	0.4	0.8	4.5	4.7
BPM7	2.6	3.7	8.1	8.3	0.7	1.4	6.7	7.0	0.3	0.6	3.0	3.1
BPM8	2.9	4.1	8.6	8.8	0.8	1.7	7.6	7.8	0.4	0.8	3.4	3.5
BPM9	4.6	7.2	12.0	12.2	2.1	5.3	14.7	15.3	0.9	2.3	6.5	6.8
BPM10	3.7	5.7	10.4	10.6	1.4	3.3	11.0	11.4	0.6	1.5	4.9	5.1
B2-3	3.0	4.3	9.3	9.5	0.9	1.9	8.8	9.1	0.4	0.8	3.9	4.1
B2-4	2.6	3.5	8.5	8.6	0.7	1.2	7.3	7.6	0.3	0.5	3.2	3.4
B2-5	2.8	3.8	8.8	9.0	0.8	1.5	8.0	8.3	0.3	0.7	3.5	3.7
BPM11	2.5	3.3	8.8	8.9	0.6	1.1	7.8	8.1	0.3	0.5	3.5	3.6
BXC4	2.3	2.7	8.7	8.8	0.5	0.8	7.7	8.0	0.2	0.3	3.4	3.5
B2	2.4	2.8	9.1	9.2	0.6	0.8	8.4	8.7	0.3	0.4	3.7	3.9
B6	2.8	3.6	10.2	10.4	0.8	1.3	10.6	11.0	0.4	0.6	4.7	4.9
BA12	2.9	3.7	10.6	10.8	0.9	1.4	11.6	12.0	0.4	0.6	5.1	5.3
BN1	2.9	3.8	10.1	10.2	0.9	1.5	10.3	10.7	0.4	0.7	4.6	4.8
BN3	2.2	3.0	7.3	7.5	0.5	0.9	5.5	5.7	0.2	0.4	2.4	2.5
BN5	3.1	4.3	10.1	10.3	1.0	1.9	10.5	10.8	0.4	0.9	4.6	4.8
BN6	3.1	5.0	7.5	7.7	1.0	2.5	5.8	6.0	0.4	1.1	2.6	2.7
BCZ3	2.8	4.5	5.1	5.2	0.8	2.1	2.6	2.7	0.4	0.9	1.2	1.2
BCZ4	3.0	4.9	6.6	6.7	0.9	2.5	4.4	4.6	0.4	1.1	2.0	2.0
BCZ5	2.8	4.2	8.3	8.4	0.8	1.8	7.0	7.3	0.4	0.8	3.1	3.2
BCZ6	4.3	7.0	10.5	10.7	1.9	5.0	11.3	11.7	0.8	2.2	5.0	5.2
BCZ7	3.7	4.8	12.7	13.0	1.4	2.4	16.5	17.1	0.6	1.1	7.3	7.6
BCZ8	3.5	5.7	6.4	6.5	1.3	3.3	4.1	4.3	0.6	1.5	1.8	1.9
BCZ9	4.0	6.4	9.7	9.9	1.6	4.2	9.6	10.0	0.7	1.9	4.3	4.4
BPA1	2.8	3.3	10.8	11.0	0.8	1.1	12.0	12.4	0.4	0.5	5.3	5.5
BPA2	3.3	4.4	11.3	11.5	1.1	2.0	13.1	13.5	0.5	0.9	5.8	6.0
BPA3	2.8	3.6	10.2	10.4	0.8	1.3	10.6	11.0	0.4	0.6	4.7	4.9
BPA4	2.8	4.0	8.8	8.9	0.8	1.6	7.8	8.1	0.4	0.7	3.5	3.6
BPA5	2.8	3.3	11.0	11.2	0.8	1.1	12.2	12.7	0.4	0.5	5.4	5.6
BPA7	2.2	2.7	8.2	8.4	0.5	0.7	6.9	7.1	0.2	0.3	3.1	3.2
BPA8	3.4	5.4	8.8	8.9	1.2	3.0	7.8	8.1	0.5	1.3	3.5	3.6
BPA9	3.0	3.4	11.6	11.8	0.9	1.2	13.8	14.3	0.4	0.5	6.1	6.3
BPA10	3.7	5.1	12.1	12.3	1.4	2.7	14.9	15.4	0.6	1.2	6.6	6.8
BPA11	3.3	4.8	9.8	10.0	1.1	2.4	9.8	10.1	0.5	1.0	4.3	4.5
BAK2	3.2	5.2	8.1	8.3	1.1	2.7	6.7	7.0	0.5	1.2	3.0	3.1
BAK3	2.9	3.7	10.6	10.8	0.9	1.4	11.6	12.0	0.4	0.6	5.1	5.3
BAK4	2.9	3.6	10.8	11.0	0.9	1.3	12.0	12.4	0.4	0.6	5.3	5.5
BAK5	3.1	5.1	7.2	7.3	1.0	2.6	5.2	5.4	0.4	1.2	2.3	2.4

BAK6	3.0	3.7	10.8	11.0	0.9	1.4	11.8	12.3	0.4	0.6	5.3	5.4
BKAN1	2.7	3.4	10.1	10.3	0.8	1.1	10.5	10.8	0.3	0.5	4.6	4.8
BKAN2	2.7	4.0	8.0	8.1	0.8	1.7	6.5	6.7	0.3	0.7	2.9	3.0
BKAN3	2.7	4.3	6.6	6.7	0.7	1.9	4.4	4.6	0.3	0.8	2.0	2.0
BKAN4	4.0	6.4	9.7	9.9	1.6	4.2	9.6	10.0	0.7	1.9	4.3	4.4
BKAN5	3.2	5.1	8.4	8.5	1.1	2.7	7.2	7.4	0.5	1.2	3.2	3.3
BKAN6	2.7	4.4	5.2	5.3	0.7	2.0	2.8	2.9	0.3	0.9	1.2	1.3
BKAN7	3.2	5.4	7.2	7.3	1.1	3.0	5.2	5.4	0.5	1.3	2.3	2.4
BKAN8	2.5	3.8	7.4	7.6	0.7	1.4	5.6	5.8	0.3	0.6	2.5	2.6
BKAN9	3.9	6.5	8.3	8.4	1.6	4.3	7.0	7.3	0.7	1.9	3.1	3.2
BKAN10	3.6	5.0	11.6	11.8	1.3	2.6	13.8	14.3	0.6	1.1	6.1	6.3

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Figure 1; a) Location map of the boulder ridges; b) Boulder ridge at Punta Venado (PV). c) Boulders at eastern Cozumel. Sites: XT: Xcaret, PV: Punta Venado, PA: Paamul, XH: XpuHa, KA: Kantinah, PL: Palladium Resort, XC: Xcacel, CT: Caleta Tankah.

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Figure 2. Agisoft photogrammetry of some boulders in the Akumal Sector. All of the measurements used in this study can be obtained from the 3D reconstructions.

376x204mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 3. Boulder transport histogram for the boulders recorded at the study sites (see Tables 1 and 2 for the boulder properties and pre-transport settings).

Figure 4. Model of a tsunami generated by an earthquake Mw 7.6 along Motagua fault showing predicted wave height in the studied area.

146x106mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 5. Post classic Maya remains SW XpuHa upper the boulder ridge

397x298mm (180 x 180 DPI)